

A MULTI-SCALE ANALYSIS FOR STRUCTURAL DESIGN OF FIBROUS COMPOSITES - M³ METHOD -

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SUMMARY: The requirements to analyze a micro-stress or a micro-strain are rising to composites and MEMS. The zooming technique and the homogenization, which can consider the macro and the micro properties for analysis, are the practical methods. However, they have some difficulties to apply to the non-uniform fields of stress or strain and to the damage problems. The mesh superposition, which can avoid these problems, will be one of the effective methods. The finite element method using mesh superposition with multi-scale that can be applied to the non-uniform field of stress or strain in the local area has been proposed. We've defined the new numerical technology as M³ (Macro-Meso-Micro) method. In this paper, the formulations of M³ method and the numerical example have been described. In addition, the method has been expanded into the damage mechanics to investigate the development of transverse crack, which may be generated in the fibre bundle as the initial damage. The results will give very important information to evaluate the safety of composites structure. It is revealed that the stresses and strains for both of macro and micro regions can be analyzed simultaneously by only one operation.

KEYWORDS: Multi-scale analysis, FEM, Damage mechanics, FRP, Transverse Crack

INTRODUCTION

While woven fabric composites have been applied widely to many structures because they have some advantages like easy handling, high lateral strength, high resistance to impact etc., they have the properties of anisotropy, heterogeneity and geometrical structure complexity. Therefore, it is very difficult to calculate directly the stress or strain act on the fabric composites with the traditional FEM.

The multi-scale analysis is one of the major techniques in both fields of the computational mechanics and the material development. The homogenization method has been applied to multi-scale analysis. But there are some problems to apply to the non-uniform fields of stress or strain and to the damage problems. As the mesh superposition can avoid these problems, it may be one of the effective methods [1]. In order to investigate the effect of a micro level like a filament on the woven structure, a new computational method that the mechanical behaviors for composites can simulate with consideration the large-scale differences is required. Therefore, we propose the finite element method using mesh superposition with 3 scales, which can be applied to the non-uniform field of stress and strain in the local area. We define the new numerical technology as M³ (Macro-Meso-Micro) method. In this paper, the formulations of M³ method and the numerical example have been described. In addition, the

method has been expanded into the damage mechanics in order to investigate the development of transverse crack [2], which may be generated in the fibre bundle as the initial damage [3][4]. This is very important information to evaluate the safety of composites structure.

FORMULATION OF M³ METHOD

Multi-scale Analysis Technique (M³ method)

A new multi-scale technique with the superimpose mesh method that can analyze the stress in a limited domain has been suggested. There are the macro ($\Omega^1 = \Omega$), the meso ($(\Omega^2: \Omega^2 \ \Omega^1)$) and the micro ($(\Omega^3: \Omega^3 \ \Omega^2)$) in a global domain (Ω) as shown in Fig.1. These meshes are different scale and superpose on each other without regard of consistency of the element and the nodal point. Γ_s is the border where surface force $\{t_s\}$ act on the border of a global domain Γ . The overlapping parts of mesh are defined as the analysis domain to express as follows.

$$\Omega^L = \Omega^1 \cup \Omega^2 \cup \Omega^3 \quad (1)$$

$$\Omega^M = (\Omega^1 \cup \Omega^2) \setminus \Omega^L \quad (2)$$

$$\Omega^G = \Omega^1 \setminus (\Omega^M \cup \Omega^L) \quad (3)$$

$$\{\mathbf{u}\} = \begin{cases} \{\mathbf{u}^G\} & \text{on } \Omega^G \\ \{\mathbf{u}^G\} + \{\mathbf{u}^M\} & \text{on } \Omega^M \\ \{\mathbf{u}^G\} + \{\mathbf{u}^M\} + \{\mathbf{u}^L\} & \text{on } \Omega^L \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 1: The concept of M-cube method and the definition of each region

Γ^{GM} and Γ^{ML} show the borders of macro – meso and meso-micro domains, respectively. The displacement in a total domain is defined as Eq. (4).

$\{\mathbf{u}^G\}$, $\{\mathbf{u}^M\}$ and $\{\mathbf{u}^L\}$ are displacements in the domain Ω^G , Ω^M and Ω^L , respectively. The suffixes G, M and L show each analysis domain same as displacement domain. In order to keep continuation condition, Eqs (5) and (6) are defined.

$$\{\mathbf{u}^M\} = \{0\} \text{ on } \Gamma^{GM} \quad (5)$$

$$\{\mathbf{u}^L\} = \{0\} \text{ on } \Gamma^{ML} \quad (6)$$

The displacement in the element is expressed with the displacement vector $\{d\}$ and shape function matrix $[\mathbf{N}]$ as follows.

$$\{\mathbf{u}^G\} = [\mathbf{N}^G] \{dG\} \quad (7)$$

$$\{\mathbf{u}^M\} = [\mathbf{N}^M] \{dM\} \quad (8)$$

$$\{\mathbf{u}^L\} = [\mathbf{N}^L] \{dL\} \quad (9)$$

Three meshes are independent and $[\mathbf{N}]$ do not have to be always similar.

The strain vector $\{e\}$ can be expressed by strain-displacement matrix $[\mathbf{B}]$ and nodal point displacement vector $\{d\}$.

$$\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}\} = \begin{cases} \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^G\} \\ \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^G\} + \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^M\} \\ \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^G\} + \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^M\} + \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^L\} \end{cases} = \begin{cases} [\mathbf{B}^G]\{\mathbf{d}^G\} \\ [\mathbf{B}^G]\{\mathbf{d}^G\} + [\mathbf{B}^M]\{\mathbf{d}^M\} \\ [\mathbf{B}^G]\{\mathbf{d}^G\} + [\mathbf{B}^M]\{\mathbf{d}^M\} + [\mathbf{B}^L]\{\mathbf{d}^L\} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

We obtain Eq. (11) for stress vector by stress - strain matrix [D].

$$\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}\} = \begin{cases} [\mathbf{D}^G]\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^G\} & \text{on } \Omega^G \\ [\mathbf{D}^M](\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^G\} + \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^M\}) & \text{on } \Omega^M \\ [\mathbf{D}^L](\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^G\} + \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^M\} + \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^L\}) & \text{on } \Omega^L \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Stiffness Equations

The principle of virtual work when the body force does not act on a structure can be expressed as follows.

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}\}^T \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}\} d\Omega = \int_{\Gamma_s} \delta\{\mathbf{u}\}^T \{\mathbf{t}_s\} d\Gamma \quad (12)$$

$\delta\{*\}$ is the quantity of virtual change of arbitrary vector $\{*\}$. When we substitute from Eq. (4) to Eq. (11) for Eq. (12), we obtain Eq. (13).

$$\begin{bmatrix} [\mathbf{K}^G] & [\mathbf{K}^{GM}] & [\mathbf{K}^{GL}] \\ [\mathbf{K}^{GM}]^T & [\mathbf{K}^M] & [\mathbf{K}^{ML}] \\ [\mathbf{K}^{GL}]^T & [\mathbf{K}^{ML}]^T & [\mathbf{K}^L] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\mathbf{d}^G\} \\ \{\mathbf{d}^M\} \\ \{\mathbf{d}^L\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \{\mathbf{F}_s^G\} \\ \{\mathbf{0}\} \\ \{\mathbf{0}\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$[\mathbf{K}^G] = \int_{\Omega^G} [\mathbf{B}^G]^T [\mathbf{D}^G] [\mathbf{B}^G] d\Omega + \int_{\Omega^M} [\mathbf{B}^G]^T [\mathbf{D}^M] [\mathbf{B}^G] d\Omega + \int_{\Omega^L} [\mathbf{B}^G]^T [\mathbf{D}^L] [\mathbf{B}^G] d\Omega \quad (14)$$

$$[\mathbf{K}^M] = \int_{\Omega^M} [\mathbf{B}^M]^T [\mathbf{D}^M] [\mathbf{B}^M] d\Omega + \int_{\Omega^L} [\mathbf{B}^M]^T [\mathbf{D}^L] [\mathbf{B}^M] d\Omega \quad (15)$$

$$[\mathbf{K}^L] = \int_{\Omega^L} [\mathbf{B}^L]^T [\mathbf{D}^L] [\mathbf{B}^L] d\Omega \quad (16)$$

$$[\mathbf{K}^{GM}] = \int_{\Omega^M} [\mathbf{B}^G]^T [\mathbf{D}^M] [\mathbf{B}^M] d\Omega + \int_{\Omega^L} [\mathbf{B}^G]^T [\mathbf{D}^L] [\mathbf{B}^M] d\Omega \quad (17)$$

$$[\mathbf{K}^{ML}] = [\mathbf{K}^{LM}]^T = \int_{\Omega^L} [\mathbf{B}^M]^T [\mathbf{D}^L] [\mathbf{B}^L] d\Omega \quad (18)$$

$$[\mathbf{K}^{GL}] = [\mathbf{K}^{LG}]^T = \int_{\Omega^L} [\mathbf{B}^G]^T [\mathbf{D}^L] [\mathbf{B}^L] d\Omega \quad (19)$$

Where, $[\mathbf{K}^G]$ is the stiffness matrix for macro-region, $[\mathbf{K}^{GM}]$ is the one of macro and meso correlation, $[\mathbf{K}^{ML}]$ is the one of meso and micro correlation and $[\mathbf{K}^{GL}]$ is the one of macro and micro correlation, respectively. $\{\mathbf{F}_s^G\}$ is the force vector for macro-mesh region and it will be expressed by Eq. (20).

$$\{\mathbf{F}_s^G\} = \int_{\Gamma_s} [\mathbf{N}^G] \{\mathbf{t}_s\} d\Gamma \quad (20)$$

For the analysis method mentioned above, we call it M^3 (M-CUBE) method after three domains of macro, meso and micro. This method has a characteristic that can grasp the mechanical behavior of three domains by only one time operation. In addition, the property of each domain can be revealed by the combined equation, because the correlation matrixes $[K^{GM}]$, $[K^{GL}]$ and $[K^{ML}]$ are included in the constitutive equation.

We can treat $[K^L]$ as same as the stiffness matrix of a conventional finite element method (FEM), but the stiffness matrixes except it are required the special computational procedure. From Eq. (17), it is recognized that the stiffness matrix $[K^{GL}]$ needs both of $[B^G]$ and $[B^L]$. We cannot calculate $[B^G]$ directly, because the Gaussian point of integral in micro-mesh defines the normalized co-ordinate system. Though we have to convert the Gaussian point into the global coordinate system, M^3 method is able to carry out as same as conventional FEM, because there is not significant distinction from the conventional FEM with technique. It is clear that a characteristic in each scale influences mutually because the macro-mesh shows the influence included both of the micro-mesh and the meso-mesh.

From the above mentioned, it is recognized that the computational procedure of M^3 method is as same as the conventional FEM and the analysis with large difference of scale like the whole structure and monofilament of a fibre reinforced plastic can be carried out by only one operation.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Verification

In order to verify the proposed procedure by M^3 method, the model shown in Fig.2 has been employed. A particle is included in a cubic material. The boundary condition and the dimension are also shown in Fig.2. The mechanical properties of each material are shown in Table 1. Fig. 3 shows the finite element meshes by M^3 method and the total number of elements and nodes of macro-, meso- and micro-meshes, respectively. The superimposed state of each mesh by M^3 method is shown in Fig.4.

Table 1: Material property

Matrix		Inclusion	
Young's modulus E_m [GPa]	Poisson's ratio ν_m	Young's modulus E_i [GPa]	Poisson's ratio ν_i
1.00×10^2	0.300	1.00×10	0.300

Fig. 2: Analytical model for verification

Fig. 3: Finite element meshes by M^3 method for the model shown in figure2

(c) Micro Mesh
Fig. 3: Continued

(a) Bird's-eye view
(b) Cross-sectional view
Fig. 4: Superimposed state of meshes by M^3 method

Fig. 5: Finite element mesh for conventional FEM

Fig. 6: Comparison of stress (σ_x) distribution

On the other hand, the fine mesh model for conventional FEM as shown in Fig.5 has been prepared to compare the stress distribution around the inserted particle with M^3 method. The total number of elements is 16896 and it has over three times as many as M^3 method has. The numerical results of stress (σ_x) distribution by both methods are shown in Fig.6. Since the both results agree well with each other, it is recognized that the M^3 method is reasonable procedure and the validity of the method has been able to demonstrate.

Stress Analysis of Woven Fabric Composites

A three dimensional heterogeneous FE model which consists of glass fiber and matrix as woven fabric composites (FRP) is employed. Fibers and matrix are treated macroscopically as anisotropy and isotropic homogeneous bodies, respectively. The fibers are arranged unidirectional in the form of each bundle with a plain-woven structure and the geometry of plain-woven is analyzed by WiseTex [5]. The model consists of three plain-woven fabric layers. The mechanical behaviors under tensile loading have been analyzed by the proposed M^3 method. Figure 7 shows the macro, meso and micro-meshes generated by 3D 8-node elements. Figure 8 shows the boundary conditions and the superimposed state of each mesh. The interface between the fibre and the resin can be modeled in the micro-mesh. The total number of nodes and elements of the micro-mesh model are 18585 and 16128, respectively. The micro-mesh is superimposed on a weft bundle of the meso-mesh, which means the fiber bundles with resin. The total number of nodes and elements of meso-mesh model are 1443 and 1056. The meso-mesh is superimposed in the center part of the macro-mesh. The total number of nodes and elements of the macro-mesh model are 1183 and 864. Three meshes can be superimposed without taking care of the matching of nodes and elements in the boundary to avoid the trouble in mesh generation.

Figure 9 shows the stress (σ_x) distributions under tensile loading ($\epsilon_x=0.1\%$) which have been analyzed with the proposed method. As the stress or the strain for macro, meso and micro-meshes can be evaluated like a microscope, it is recognized that the proposed method is very useful for the estimation of mechanical behaviors to the structure with complex architecture.

Fig. 7: Finite element models of woven fabric composites by the proposed M^3 method

(a) A meso-mesh superimposed on a macro-mesh

(b) Micro-mesh superimposed on a meso-mesh

Fig.8: Boundary conditions and superimposed state of meshes

Fig.9: Results of stress (σ_x) distributions of woven fabric composites ($\varepsilon_x=0.1\%$)

Damage Analysis of Woven Fabric Composites

A three dimensional heterogeneous FE model which consists of one woven fabric layer is employed. Fibers and matrix are treated macroscopically as anisotropic and isotropic homogeneous bodies respectively. The occurrence of damage can be predicted by the classical failure criteria such as Maximum strain theory, Hoffman or Tsai-Wu criteria. In this paper, Hoffman failure criterion has been applied. The damage modes are also classified by the ratio of stress to strength for the damaged element [2][3][6]. The damage modes for composites are classified macroscopically as shown in Fig.10. However, the anisotropic damage model for fibers and the isotropic damage model for matrix are utilized to simulate the microscopic damage propagation.

In order to examine the accuracy of the numerical results, we have conducted uniaxial tensile test. The testing apparatus with laser microscope and the geometry of specimen are shown in Fig.11. The generation of damage such as initial crack is observed by laser microscope while loading condition.

Fig.12 shows the finite element model for test specimen, which is made of woven fabric composites with glass fiber and vinyl ester resin. The macro model deals with a half of specimen. The micro model is produced from the real fiber volume fraction for the bundle, which has been observed by microscope, and it is 62.75%. The adopted mechanical properties for simulation are shown in table 2. Figure 13 shows the numerical results of the stress

distributions for macro, meso and micro-models under a uniform tensile strain (0.33% strain). The stress distribution for a part of macro model, where meso-mesh is superimposed, is generated by the stretch of the bundle of warp direction. The tensile stress is also generated on the surface of weft bundle. In addition, it is revealed that the tensile stress is taken place in the resin part between the filaments.

Damage mode	Anisotropic damage model for fiber bundle				Isotropic damage model for matrix
	Mode L	Mode T & LT	Mode Z & ZL	Mode TZ	
Maximum stress-to-strength ratio	$\frac{\sigma_L^2}{F_L^t F_L^c}$	$\frac{\sigma_T^2}{F_T^t F_T^c}$ or $\left(\frac{\tau_{LT}}{F_{LT}^s}\right)^2$	$\frac{\sigma_Z^2}{F_Z^t F_Z^c}$ or $\left(\frac{\tau_{ZL}}{F_{ZL}^s}\right)^2$	$\left(\frac{\tau_{TZ}}{F_{TZ}^s}\right)^2$	—
Damage tensor $\begin{bmatrix} D_L & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & D_T & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & D_Z \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$

σ_i, τ_{ij} : stress, F^t, F^t : tensile strength, F^c, F^c : compressive strength, F^s : shearing strength

Fig.10: Classification of the damage mode based on damage mechanic

Fig.11: Testing apparatus of tensile test and specimen of woven fabric composites

(a) Macro-mesh model

(b) Meso-mesh model

(c) Micro-mesh model

Fig.12: Finite element models of a woven fabric composites specimen under tensile test by the proposed M³ method

From these numerical results, it can be estimated that the initial transverse crack will occur among the filaments center of weft bundle. The numerical and the experimental results for the crack propagation under 0.57% and 0.78% tensile strain are shown in Fig.14. In Fig.14, the colored element indicates the damaged ones. From these results, it is declared that the mechanical behaviors can be simulated microscopically by the proposed method.

Table 2: Mechanical properties

	Young's modulus (GPa)			Shear modulus (GPa)			Poisson's ratio		
Glass fiber	73.0			30.1			0.220		
Resin	3.33			1.28			0.300		
Fiber bundle	E_L	E_T	E_Z	G_{TZ}	G_{ZL}	G_{LT}	ν_{TZ}	ν_{ZL}	ν_{LT}
V_f 62.75%	47.1	14.3	14.3	5.72	5.60	5.60	0.250	0.070	0.230

Fig.13: A stress distribution of σ_x for each model under tensile loading

(a) Under 0.57% strain

(b) Under 0.78% strain

Fig.14: Numerical and experimental results of the occurrence and the propagation of the transverse crack under tensile loading

CONCLUSION

The zooming technique of FEM, which can consider the macro and the micro properties for analysis, is one of the practical ones. However, in case of the generation of small damage like a crack, we can't apply the technique to the simulation, because a little change of mechanical property in micro region is not reflected to the macro region. We will have the requirements that want to analyze the mechanical behaviors for the whole structure with the consideration of the microstructure like a filament. To meet the above requirements, the numerical system by M^3 method has been developed. In order to verify the M^3 method, a numerical model with a particle in material has been prepared. The mechanical behaviors have been analyzed by the conventional FEM and M^3 method, and the results have been compared. As both of them have a good agreement, the validity of the developed numerical system by M^3 method has been demonstrated. In addition, it is revealed that the stresses and strains for both of macro and micro regions can be analyzed simultaneously by only one operation.

As the numerical example, the stress and the strain neighborhoods the filaments in woven fabric composites under tensile loading have been simulated microscopically by M^3 method. The crack propagation can be also simulated by M^3 method in which the damage mechanics is considered. Since the effect of microstructure on the macrostructure can be taken into the consideration and the numerical analysis can be carried out with seamless from macro region to micro region, it has been recognized that M^3 method described in this paper is a very useful for composites field.

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